

VOWEL EQUALENCE IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Radjabov Nasir Nasimovich,

Professor of the Department of Teaching Languages of the Public Security University of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Doctor of Philosophy on Philological Sciences, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

In order to identify the similar and distinctive features of the vowel phonemes and their positional variants in English and Uzbek, the vowel systems of these languages should be sub-grouped in the following way from the point of their acoustic and orthographic similarities:

a) *the phonemes that coincide partially from acoustic and orthographic view point in the contrasted languages: /ɪ/, /e/, /ɒ/, /ʊ/. Each of these phonemes is expressed in written form with one letter in Uzbek, with several letters and letter combinations in English;*

b) *the vowels differentiated from orthographic view point, though coincided acoustically: /ʌ/. This phoneme is expressed with different letters in the contrasted languages;*

c) *the vowels differentiated from acoustic point of view, though coincided partially from orthographic view point: the vowel phoneme /ʌ/ in Uzbek and /æ/ in English can be example to it;*

d) *the vowels coincided from neither acoustic nor orthographic points of view in the contrasted languages. Such phonemes are important as they exist only in one language and not to have their equivalent in the second language. For example, /ɔ̃/ in Uzbek does not exist in English, whereas the phonemes /ɑ:/, /ɔ:/, /ɜ:/, /ə/, /i:/, /u:/, /eɪ/, /aɪ/, /ɔɪ/, /aʊ/, /əʊ/, /ɪə/, /εə/, /ʊə/ in English are not available in Uzbek.*

The vowel systems of the languages being contrasted is incompatible both in terms of its structure and the number of phonemes in it and their positional appearances. In English, the vowel phonemes can mainly have four or six positional

variants. As to Uzbek, mainly three positional variants of vowel phonemes are differentiated¹ (See Table 1).

¹ In Uzbek, the combinatory variants of the vowels are also characteristic as well as their positional variants. The linguists, who consider that the vowel system of the Uzbek literary language consists of six phonemes, explain the phonemes /ɪ, e, ʌ/ as front vowels, whereas the phonemes /ʊ, ɔ̃, ɒ/ as back vowels, and say that back allophones of the front vowels and front allophones of the back vowels are considered to be their combinatory variants which occur under the influence of neighboring consonants [Абдуазизов А. Ўзбек тили фонологияси ва морфонологияси. 2-нашр. – Т.: Ўқитувчи, 2010; Маҳмудов Қ. Ўзбек тилининг тарихий фонетикаси. – Т.: Ижод нашр., 2006]. According to the linguists, who think that there are more than six vowel phonemes in the Uzbek language, the vowels /ɪ, ʌ, ʊ, ɔ̃/ have front and back variants (front vowels: /и/, /й/, /ё/, /ä/; back vowels: /ы/, /у/, /о/, /ə/) and each of them

Table 1
Positional variants of the vowel phonemes

In English		
The phonemes /e/, /i:/, /ɪ/, /aɪ/, /ɪə/, /ɛə/ are mainly represented in their six different positional variants:	The phonemes /ɒ/, /ʊ/ /ʌ/ /æ/, /ɑ:/, /ɔ:/, /ɜ:/, /ə/, /u:/, /eɪ/, /əʊ/, /ʊə/ are mainly represented in their five different positional variants:	The phonemes /ɔɪ/, /aʊ/ are mainly represented in their four different positional variants:
<p>invariant (it is the main view of the phoneme): city [ˈsɪtɪ];</p> <p>variation (it is shorter than invariant in a closed syllable that ends up with a voiced consonant): pig [pɪɡ];</p> <p>variation (it is much shorter than invariant in a closed syllable that ends up with a voiceless consonant): pick [pɪk];</p> <p>variation (it is shorter and weaker in unstressed syllable): pity [ˈpɪtɪ];</p> <p>variant (it resembles other sounds because of being unstressed): geopolitical [.dʒi:əʊpəˈlɪtɪkəl] - geopolitics [.dʒi:əʊˈpələtɪks], peculiar [pɪˈeɪkjʊ:lɪə].</p>	<p>invariant (it is the main view of the phoneme): four [fɔː];</p> <p>variation (it is shorter than invariant in a closed syllable that ends up with a voiced consonant): ford [fɔːd];</p> <p>variation (it is much shorter than invariant in a closed syllable that ends up with a voiceless consonant): court [kɔːt];</p> <p>variation (it is shorter and weaker in unstressed syllable): audition [ɔːˈdɪʃn];</p> <p>variant (it resembles another sound because of being unstressed): reform [rɪˈfɔːm] - reformation [refɔːˈmeɪʃən].</p>	<p>invariant (it is the main view of the phoneme): now [naʊ];</p> <p>variation (it is shorter than invariant in a closed syllable that ends up with a voiced consonant): loud [laʊd];</p> <p>variation (it is much shorter than invariant in a closed syllable that ends up with a voiceless consonant): lout [laʊt];</p> <p>variation (it is shorter and weaker in unstressed syllable): outrageous [aʊˈreɪdʒəs].</p>
In Uzbek		
Each of the six vowel phonemes of the Uzbek language is mainly represented in three positional variants:		
invariant (the main view of the phoneme): бир [bɪr];		
variation (shorter and weaker in unstressed syllable): бироз [bɪˈrɒz];		
variation (very short between two voiceless consonants in the following syllables: CVC, CV-CV) ² : чиқ /tʃɪq/, шиши /ʃ(ɪ)ʃɪ/.		

The fact that vowels in English have more positional variants than in Uzbek cause Uzbek native speakers to have difficulty in mastering their pronunciation. Having different positional variants of English vowels leads to a number of difficulties in learning the pronunciation of not only the vowels that don't have their

is regarded as an independent phoneme [Тўйчибоев Б. Ўзбек тилининг таркият босқичлари. – Т.: Ўқитувчи, 1996; Данияров Х. Опыт изучения джекающих (кыпчакских) диалектов в сравнении с узбекским литературным языком. – Т.: Фан, 1975]. Our research is based on the first approach because of the vowel systems of the English and Uzbek literary languages being chosen as the object of this research.

² The voiced feature of consonants, which come in the post-position of a word consisting of one syllable, is not changed in English, but is neutralized in Uzbek. The neutralization of voiced consonants in post-position does not imply the need for interpretation of the variations of the vowels in the syllable ended with voiced consonants as a separate positional variation in the Uzbek language.

equivalents in Uzbek, but also the vowels which are acoustically similar in both languages.

The English phonemes /ɪ/, /e/, /ʌ/, /ɒ/, /ʊ/ are acoustically similar to the Uzbek vowels /ɪ/, /e/, /ʌ/, /ɒ/, /ʊ/. However, these phonemes cannot be fully equivalent because of the difference in their positional variants. This situation indicates that acoustically similar phonemes in the contrasted languages are not entirely equivalent as a sum of sounds. The difference in the types of vowel phonemes and their positional variants in the languages under study have shown that they can not be fully equivalent. In this regard, it is desirable to use the term of semi-equivalent when it comes to speak about the degree of equivalence of vowel phonemes in the English and Uzbek languages.

This problem causes a number of difficulties in the process of teaching the pronunciation of English phonemes in the Uzbek audience. Overcoming these difficulties requires, first of all, a thorough study of the linguistic factors that cause the phonetic and phonological interference of vowels in English and Uzbek. In contrasted languages, two types of linguistic factors, which lead to the Phonetic and Phonological interference, should be distinguished: **1) linguistic factors directly connected with the vowel system:** a) *difference in the structure of the vowel systems;* b) *specific peculiarities of vowels from articulatory-acoustic point of view;* c) *occurring of the state of being unstressed differently;* d) *disproportion in the positional variants of vowel phonemes.*

2) linguistic factors indirectly connected with the vowel system: *the distinction in the phoneme orthography and the orthoepy of vowel letters in the contrasted languages.*

The fact that the writing system of the Uzbek literary language is based on the principle of "One phoneme - one letter" which means one vowel phoneme is expressed only with one letter whereas the literary English writing system is based on the principle of "One phoneme - several letters" that means one vowel phoneme may be represented with more than one letter or letter combinations in writing³ is the main factor which causes for the interference *in the phoneme orthography and the orthoepy of vowel letters.*

From this point of view, the following two types of linguistic interference occur in teaching the pronunciation of English vowels to Uzbek learners:

- a) the phonetic and phonological interference,
- b) the orthographic interference.

The above mentioned linguistic factors, which cause the phonetic - phonological and orthographic interference of the vowel phonemes in the contrasted languages, impede the pronunciation of English vowels properly. The cause for this interference is on the one hand, the pronunciation habits of Uzbek

³ Раджабов Н.Н. Инглиз ва ўзбек тилларида вокализм системасининг фонологик жиҳатдан чоғиштирма тадқиқи: филол. фан. б-ча фалсафа д-ри дисс. – Тошкент, – 2018., 139-бет. (Б.170).

people are based on the native language standards, and on the other hand, Uzbek native speakers have lack of practice to pronounce English vowel phonemes according to the norms of received pronunciation. Taking into account these types of interference in the process of mastering the pronunciation of the English language serves to eliminate the phonetic-phonological and orthographic interference of vowels caused by the influence of the native language, resulting in a more efficient process of language learning.

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